

A Comparative Analysis of BSE and NSE Indices During Major Economic Crisis: A Study of the 2008 Financial Crisis and the COVID-19 Shock

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ABSTRACT

With India continuing to be one of the fastest-growing economies, rapidly approaching the \$5 trillion GDP target, total savings and investment in stock markets are expected to increase. Stock market Indices reflect the overall market sentiment and play a vital role in influencing investments. They are used as benchmarks against which funds are evaluated. In this study, we compared the performance of three Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) Indices and three National Stock Exchange (NSE) indices regarding volatility and returns during the two major economic shocks of the Global Financial Crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic. High contemporaneous correlation, similar central tendencies, and absence of Granger causality between indices with similar composition indicate that the two major domestic stock exchanges, namely the Bombay Stock Exchange and the National Stock Exchange, are well integrated. There was no significant lead-lag relationship observed between the indices during the period March 2019 to March 2023, except between Sensex and Nifty 50. This indicates that stocks on both exchanges generally responded to common market-wide information simultaneously. The possibility of gains for investors, through arbitrage and diversification between the two stock exchanges, was therefore limited.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Stock indices are a weighted average of prices of selected stocks and serve as key benchmarks for assessing the health of equity markets. Their movements reflect market sentiments and are interpreted as signals guiding investment decisions. In India, the Sensex, Nifty 50, BSE 500, and NSE 500 are among the most tracked indices by investors, policymakers, and financial institutions. All these indices differ not only in the composition but also in their sectoral exposure, and consequently have different risk-return characteristics. In this study, we undertook a comparative analysis of these indices to understand their performance in terms of returns, volatility, and co-movement during different market stress levels. Since the 2008 Global Financial Crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic resulted in massive economic turmoil, we focused on these two crises to draw important lessons that would aid both retail and institutional investors in making informed decisions during periods of chaos.

In addition, the performance of two sector-specific indices, namely Nifty Financial Services and BSE Financial Services, was also examined to capture the behaviour of a critical sector that can drive or reflect broader market trends. While the choice of financial services indices to capture the financial

crisis is quite obvious, we felt the movement in these indices would reflect the credit stress and the general economic downturn and uncertainty associated with the pandemic.

India has a long history of trading in stocks. The origin of the Indian securities market may be traced back to as early as 1875. The two largest stock exchanges in India are the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) and the National Stock Exchange (NSE). BSE is the oldest stock exchange in Asia, and as of May 2025, the market capitalization of BSE-listed companies was \$ 4.93 trillion. NSE is one of the world's largest exchanges and the first to implement screen-based trading in India. As of March 2025, the total market capitalisation of companies listed in the NSE was \$4.8 trillion. The BSE Sensex comprises 30 of the largest, most liquid, and actively traded companies listed on the Bombay Stock Exchange, and has adequate representation of the key sectors of the Indian economy. The Nifty 50 is a broader Index than the Sensex as it includes the top 50 companies that are actively traded on the National Stock Exchange. Like the Sensex, it is also based on stocks representing important sectors of the economy. The BSE 500 Index includes the top 500 companies listed on BSE Ltd and provides a broad representation of the market, for it covers all major industries

in the economy. The Nifty 500 is based on the top 500 companies ranked in terms of market capitalization and trading frequency. The BSE Financial Services is an Index consisting of companies included in the BSE AllCap (comprising BSE LargeCap, BSE MidCap, and BSE SmallCap) and classified as members of the finance sector. The Nifty Financial Services Index measures the movement in stock prices of banks, financial institutions, housing finance, insurance companies, and other financial services companies.

2. METHODOLOGY

The BSE and NSE websites provide continuous data on the three BSE and the four NSE indices. The Nifty Total Market Index is based on all the stocks listed on the NSE and is therefore the most suitable index for measuring market returns. Daily closing price data on all these indices were collected for the periods August 2006 to April 2010 and March 2019 to March 2023. The study's objective guided the choice of the time frames to understand the behaviour of various indices during periods of major economic crisis. The periods of the 2008 Global Financial Crisis and the COVID-19 pandemic are associated with heightened turbulence and instability in financial markets. While isolating the effect of these macroeconomic shocks on the performance of the sample indices will have immense value for all market participants, clearly identifying the start and end of these crises was a huge challenge. We therefore conducted the Quandt Likelihood Ratio (QLR) test for structural breaks with unknown break date. However, the validity of the break date so determined could not be established as the residuals of pre- and post-break period regressions using our vector autoregression (VAR) model did not satisfy the assumptions of normality and constant variance.

Our choice of the study period and its further segmentation into pre-crisis, crisis, and post-crisis periods was therefore based on the following reasoning. While India did not face the collapse of any large financial institution as a result of the bursting of the housing market bubble in the U.S, our financial markets did experience increased stress. Stock markets faced a liquidity crisis as FIIs pulled out funds. Redemption pressures on mutual funds also increased. The Sensex fell by 1,408 points on January 21, 2008, and by the end of the year was at 9,716 points. During August 2007, hedge funds and many banks in the U.S found themselves stranded with liquidity problems as the market viewed the mortgage-based securities, held in substantial amounts by these financial entities, as toxic assets. The major Central Banks of the world, therefore, had to inject liquidity into the credit market. In India, stock markets suffered a major loss, with the Sensex falling by 643 points on August 16, 2007, due to an across-the-board sale of stocks. The financial crisis spread across countries, and many economies suffered a fall

in GDP. By many accounts, the recession in the U.S ended by June 2009. The Indian stock market, however, had shown signs of recovery by May 2009 itself. Therefore, we identified the period August 2007 to April 2009 as the time when the crisis manifested itself most intensely. Similarly, for the COVID-19 shock, the announcement of nationwide lockdown (March 2020) and the start of international travel (March 2022) after the COVID-19 pandemic ban were taken as the beginning and end periods of the pandemic.

To establish a baseline for stock index movements and assess their behavior during the recovery period, our study included one year before and one year following the identified crisis period. Thus, the two periods had a total excess return data for 923 and 1012 days, respectively. These two periods were further divided into three sub-periods identified as pre-crisis, crisis, and post-crisis periods. For the 2008 financial crisis, the period from August 2006 to July 2007 was considered as the pre-crisis period, August 2007 to April 2009 as the crisis period, and May 2009 to April 2010 as the post-crisis period. Similarly, for the pandemic period, the pre-crisis, crisis, and post-crisis periods were identified as March 2019 to February 2020, March 2020 to March 2022, and April 2022 to March 2023, respectively.

The daily closing value of the various indices was noted. The log returns on these indices were calculated using the formula $\ln(I_t / I_{t-1})$, where I_t and I_{t-1} are the Indices recorded in the current and the previous trading period, respectively. The data on the rate of interest on savings accounts offered by SBI over the years was collected from its website. In the next step, the interest rate on savings account, calculated on a per-day basis (a proxy for the rate of return on a risk-free asset), was subtracted from these returns to get excess returns on indices. Time series data have to be tested for stationarity to avoid spurious inferences. A unit root test was done on the excess returns series of all the indices. The excess returns on each of the six indices were regressed on excess returns on the Nifty Total Market index to calculate the 'beta' of each index, i.e.

$$I_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_i I_{mt} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots(1)$$

$$V_{i=1..6}$$

Here, I_{it} is the excess return on Nifty 50, Nifty 500, Nifty Financial Services, Sensex, BSE 500, and BSE Financial Services indices, and I_{mt} is the excess return on the Nifty Total Market Index. Beta (β) of an index is a measure of systematic risk or its volatility compared to the market. Using the mean and standard deviation of excess returns, as well as the beta of each index, we calculated several measures of risk-adjusted returns. Correlation analysis and tests for predictive causation between the various indices, using the Gretl software, were also conducted to draw inferences regarding co-movements between the indices.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the finance literature, a substantial body of research focuses on the behaviour of stock market indices. Popular themes of research include modelling the effects of various macroeconomic indicators on stock indices, analysing the performance of indices during major economic disturbances, examining the correlation between indices of different countries, etc.

Chauhan et al. (2025) explored the relationship between select macroeconomic indicators and returns on various sectoral indices. The study found that macroeconomic indicators affect index returns in both the short run and long run, and the effect varies across sectors. Two indicators that demonstrated contrasting levels of influence on sectoral indices were foreign institutional investment— which significantly impacted all indices except the IT Sector Index— and the exchange rate, which showed no significant effect on any of the sectoral indices.

Using daily data on nine BSE broad market indices for the period 2011 to 2020, Elangovan et al. (2022) found the Indian stock market to be weak-form inefficient, as their study did not find empirical support for the random walk hypothesis.

Pandey (2023) examined the influence of three macroeconomic variables, namely oil price, gold price, and exchange rate, on various sectoral indices in the Indian stock market. The author found that these macro variables have long-term links with the IT sector Index and short-run correlations with indices representing FMCG, Finance, Healthcare, IT, and Realty sectors.

Another popular area of research has been the study of the behavior of indices during turbulent periods. Olbrys and Majewska (2022) studied 36 stock market indices of European and U.S markets and analysed the performance of indices during the Global Financial Crisis period of 2007-2009 and the COVID-19 pandemic period of 2020-2021. They used the Sample Entropy algorithm (SampEn) to show that the volatility in equity market indices decreased during turbulent periods, increasing the regularity and predictability of the returns on indices. Joshi and Joshi (2022) found sector-specific herding behaviour in both bullish and bearish states in the Indian stock market (BSE) during the 2015-2020 period. A similar study on NSE by Sharma and Lodha (2024) found anti-herding behaviour before the COVID outbreak and significant herding behaviour in FMCG, Auto, and Pharma sectoral Indices after the outbreak of COVID-19.

Singh and Shaik (2021) used an event study methodology to assess the short-run effect of the WHO's announcements regarding COVID-19 on five sectoral indices of three different countries (world, developed, and emerging). The study found that the indices of developed countries registered a greater fall than the indices of emerging markets following

such announcements. Amongst the sectoral indices, pharma and healthcare indices showed positive abnormal returns, while hotel and airline indices suffered significant price falls. The Information Technology Index initially fell sharply but soon showed recovery as the world shifted to digital solutions for different activities.

Correlation between various global indices has been another well-researched topic. Derbali et al. (2021) found dynamic conditional correlation (DCC) between Chinese stock market indices and some international stock market indices was significant after the COVID-19 outbreak. The spillover effect of the Chinese Indices on the selected countries' stock market indices was shown using DCC-GARCH models. The study found that the pandemic had only a short-term impact on the volatility of international stock market indices.

Lingaraja et al. (2015) examined the correlation between the returns of six select Asian stock market indices between 2000 and 2012. Such correlation analysis provides useful insights to foreign institutional investors, portfolio managers, and policymakers. In the study of Chinese stock market indices for the period 2008 to 2012, Valukonis (2013) found that Chinese and global market indices exhibited similar trends before the 2008 financial crisis but had differing trends after 2009. The study found the U.S and Chinese stock indices to be weakly correlated and that the returns on indices of Chinese markets were negative despite the high growth rate in GDP during the study period.

Researchers have used measures of correlation between indices to examine the question of financial integration. Madaleno and Pinho (2012) examined the time-varying nature of the correlation between major stock market indices. They found that correlations and comovements are higher for markets that are geographically and economically closer than distant markets. However, financial contagion during a financial crisis leads to strong comovements between the indices across countries in the long run. Potharla and Aparna (2012) studied the degree of stock market integration by examining the correlation between select global indices. The study found BSE Sensex to have a strong association with NYSE and Hang Seng (Hong Kong stock market Index)

Mukherjee (2007) explored the integration of the Indian stock market with major global markets. The study found that the stock markets' influence on one another intensified after 2000. Factors that led to increased financial integration between various markets include the opening up of economies, increased foreign trade, the rise of MNCs, and the automation of exchanges. The author argued that greater financial integration between capital markets had reduced profitability associated with international diversification and that there was a convergence among markets.

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Profitable trading opportunities in the Indian stock markets have been identified by many researchers (see, for example, Shet et al. (2023), Srinivasan (2010)). Dsouza and Mallikarjunappa (2015) applied various tests, such as the autocorrelation test, the Runs test, the unit root test, the variance ratio test, and models from the Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) family, to show that BSE Indices do not follow a random walk. The authors, therefore, argued that historical stock prices are of great significance to market participants, and investors can use technical analysis to beat the market.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 STATIONARITY TEST

Time series data have to be examined for the presence of a unit root or trend for meaningful analysis of the data. If the

series under consideration does not have a constant mean and variance, it should be either detrended or differenced to achieve stationarity, based on whether the variable displays a deterministic trend or not. Given that financial market variables, such as prices, exhibit non-stationarity due to stochastic rather than deterministic trends, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test with a constant was applied to the excess returns on all seven indices. The null hypothesis for the ADF test is that the series under consideration is non-stationary. Table 1 shows the tau statistic of the ADF test and the associated p-values for all seven indices across the different study periods. From the table, it is clear that the excess returns series of all seven indices were stationary for all the periods considered.

TABLE 1. STATIONARITY TEST FOR THE VARIOUS PERIODS

Index	Aug 2006 - April 2010	Aug 2006- July 2007	Aug 2007- April 2009	May 2009- April 2010	March 2019- March 2023	March 2019 -Feb 2020	March 2020- March 2022	April 2022— March 2023
	Tau Statistic (p-value)							
Sensex	-10.3538 (2.41E-20)	-6.02566 (1.04E-07)	-19.0049 (1.84E-45)	-11.9358 (1.69E-25)	-9.29461 (5.76E-17)	-9.71069 (2.79E-18)	-6.95528 (4.37E-10)	-14.958 (4.88E-35)
BSE 500	-9.66552 (3.88E-18)	-5.54627 (1.37E-06)	-18.2367 (8.81E-44)	-14.6525 (4.05E-34)	-10.4743 (9.81E-21)	-13.5258 (1.27E-30)	-7.06923 (2.15E-10)	-14.5472 (8.45E-34)
BSE Fin Services	-26.1353 (3.79E-52)	-7.50694 (1.31E-11)	-17.7772 (1.06E-42)	-3.20723 (1.96E-02)	-11.0392 (1.43E-22)	-13.7094 (3.33E-31)	-6.65937 (2.66E-09)	-14.0714 (2.46E-32)
NIFTY 50	-10.237 (5.74E-20)	-5.86118 (2.57E-07)	-19.3317 (3.97E-46)	-6.06215 (8.48E-08)	-9.1565 (1.56E-16)	-9.58558 (6.96E-18)	-6.90274 (6.04E-10)	-15.0359 (2.86E-35)
NIFTY 500	-9.72971 (2.43E-18)	-5.50796 (1.67E-06)	-18.4404 (3.05E-44)	-4.71627 (7.49E-05)	-10.4608 (1.09E-20)	-13.5663 (9.43E-31)	-7.03895 (2.60E-10)	-14.5412 (8.81E-34)
Nifty Fin Services	-10.6394 (2.86E-21)	-7.52151 (1.20E-11)	-18.1828 (1.17E-43)	-7.43686 (2.07E-11)	-11.1921 (4.53E-23)	-9.9137 (6.28E-19)	-6.09469 (7.07E-08)	-14.3248 (4.05E-33)
Nifty TMI	-9.6776 (3.55E-18)	-5.47507 (1.97E-06)	-18.3627 (4.56E-44)	-4.6981 (8.12E-05)	-10.4433 (1.24E-20)	-13.5136 (1.39E-30)	-7.01957 (2.93E-10)	-14.4811 (1.34E-33)

Note: p-values are shown in parentheses

4.2 SUMMARY STATISTICS

Tables 2, 3, and 4 show the summary statistics of the excess returns series of the six indices that were evaluated for this study. We report the mean and standard deviation (s.d.) of

excess returns, along with the standard deviation of negative excess returns for the broad period covering the two crises in Table 2. Tables 3 and 4 show the same statistics for the

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segmented periods of the Global Financial Crisis and COVID-19.

TABLE 2. SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR THE TWO CRISIS PERIODS

Index	Aug 2006 - April 2010			March 2019- March 2023		
	Mean	S.D.	S.D. (Neg.)	Mean	S.D.	S.D. (Neg.)
Sensex	4.363E-04	0.02072	0.01526	4.147E-04	0.01330	0.01163
BSE 500	5.091E-04	0.01992	0.01572	4.066E-04	0.01268	0.01151
BSE Fin Services	7.874E-04	0.02510	0.01829	3.070E-04	0.01704	0.01482
NIFTY 50	4.657E-04	0.02056	0.01554	3.927E-04	0.01310	0.01149
NIFTY 500	4.819E-04	0.01982	0.01565	4.031E-04	0.01263	0.01148
Nifty Fin Services	8.847E-04	0.02603	0.01859	3.927E-04	0.01716	0.01472

TABLE 3. SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR THE GLOBAL FINANCIAL CRISIS PERIOD

Index	Aug 2006- July 2007			Aug 2007- April 2009			May 2009- April 2010		
	Mean	S.D.	S.D. (Neg.)	Mean	S.D.	S.D. (Neg.)	Mean	S.D.	S.D. (Neg.)
Sensex	1.389E-03	0.01200	0.01007	-8.224E-04	0.02567	0.01777	1.652E-03	0.01780	0.00977
BSE 500	1.545E-03	0.01158	0.01027	-9.892E-04	0.02466	0.01831	2.055E-03	0.01705	0.01039
BSE Fin Services	2.098E-03	0.01487	0.01168	-9.966E-04	0.03109	0.02083	2.551E-03	0.02131	0.01244
NIFTY 50	1.371E-03	0.01229	0.01045	-7.169E-04	0.02527	0.01822	1.597E-03	0.01794	0.01021
NIFTY 500	1.469E-03	0.01165	0.01023	-9.186E-04	0.02454	0.0182	1.908E-03	0.01693	0.01045
Nifty Fin Services	2.319E-03	0.01652	0.01264	-8.728E-04	0.03197	0.02085	2.477E-03	0.02199	0.01304

TABLE 4. SUMMARY STATISTICS FOR THE COVID-19 PERIOD

Index	March 2019-Feb 2020			March 2020- March 2022			April 2022— March 2023		
	Mean	S.D.	S.D. (Neg.)	Mean	S.D.	S.D. (Neg.)	Mean	S.D.	S.D. (Neg.)
Sensex	1.821E-04	0.00926	0.00574	7.457E-04	0.01622	0.01544	-4.507E-05	0.00933	0.00587
BSE 500	3.656E-05	0.00928	0.00591	8.568E-04	0.01524	0.01541	-1.657E-04	0.00925	0.00634
BSE Fin Services	4.012E-04	0.01245	0.00822	3.377E-04	0.02090	0.01887	1.505E-04	0.01100	0.00754
NIFTY 50	6.645E-05	0.00935	0.00582	7.830E-04	0.01590	0.01533	-9.819E-05	0.00929	0.00592
NIFTY 500	4.024E-05	0.00927	0.0059	8.481E-04	0.01516	0.01532	-1.658E-04	0.00926	0.00635
Nifty Fin Services	6.870E-04	0.01233	0.00822	3.778E-04	0.02108	0.01867	1.340E-04	0.01111	0.00741

Table 2 shows that the mean excess returns on all the sample indices during the COVID-19 crisis were lower than those during the 2008 financial crisis. The lower returns were, however, associated with lower risk as measured by s.d. of returns or s.d. of negative returns. Broad-based Indices like BSE 500 and Nifty 500 had lower s.d. than benchmark indices and sector-specific indices. This aligns with the basic notion in finance that diversification reduces risk. Given the fact that, more than volatility in returns, what matters to investors is the potential loss in the value of an investment, we calculated the downside risk of each index. The s.d. of negative returns of an index is a measure of the potential loss under adverse market conditions and is a suitable indicator of downside risk. Here again, as expected, indices based on a diversified set of stocks had lower downside risk than the sector-specific indices.

From Table 3, it is clear that the mean excess returns on all the indices worsened and were negative during the period August 2007 to April 2009, when stock markets around the world, including India, suffered a huge decline due to the collapse of major financial institutions and the U.S. housing market bubble. Moreover, markets became extremely volatile, and s.d. in excess returns increased for all indices. The financial services indices suffered the most in terms of an increase in s.d. This period also saw large downswings dominating. The markets recovered after May 2009 and delivered higher returns as compared to the pre-crisis period of August 2006 to July 2007.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the mean excess returns on benchmark indices and broad-based indices were higher from March 2020 to March 2022, when the pandemic was creating havoc worldwide, as compared to the pre-COVID period of March 2019 to February 2020. This is not surprising, considering that governments were injecting liquidity into the market, which led to a fall in interest rates and made equities more attractive. In addition to measures that protected the vulnerable sections from the harmful consequences of this crisis, fiscal measures like tax relief and credit support to sectors, and production-linked incentives to boost manufacturing, boosted investor sentiment and helped in the recovery of the market. The fall in mean excess returns on both the financial sector indices is a reflection of the differential impact of stimulus packages on various sectors. This period saw a surge in returns on the IT and pharma sectors, whereas the possibility of increased loan defaults owing to a decline in economic activity adversely affected stocks of banks and NBFCs. However, the risk of investing in stocks increased as reflected in the increase in s.d. and heightened volatility in negative returns during this period. In the subsequent year, as inflation rates spiked, central banks increased interest rates and, consequently, stock valuations

declined. The mean excess returns on Sensex, BSE 50, Nifty 50, and Nifty 500 became negative, whereas the financial sector indices delivered lower but positive mean excess returns. The decrease in mean excess returns was accompanied by a decrease in risk as measured by s.d. and s.d.(neg) of mean excess returns.

4.3 TEST FOR EQUALITY IN MEAN RETURNS ACROSS MARKETS

We explored the differences in mean excess returns across exchanges by undertaking a ‘paired t-test’ between comparable indices. This would help us infer whether the difference in mean excess returns between the following pairs of indices is statistically significant.

The pairs of indices considered were:
Sensex and Nifty 50
BSE 500 and Nifty 500
BSE Fin Services and Nifty Fin Services

The null and alternative hypotheses are
 $H_0 : \mu_{diff} = 0$
 $H_A : \mu_{diff} \neq 0$

The test statistic is $t = \frac{\bar{X}_{diff}}{s.d._{diff}/\sqrt{n}}$

Here, μ_{diff} refers to the population mean of the difference in excess returns between the two indices
 \bar{X}_{diff} and $s.d._{diff}$ are the sample mean and standard deviation of the difference in excess returns between the two indices
 n is the number of paired observations

The ‘paired t-test’ assumes that the differences in mean excess returns are normally distributed. The Jarque-Bera test for normality was undertaken to verify the same. Under the null hypothesis that the differences in mean excess returns are normally distributed, the JB statistic would be close to zero, and the associated p-value would be high. Since the number of paired observations in all the periods was quite high, the ‘paired t test’ would still be valid even if the null hypothesis of normality is rejected in the Jarque-Bera test.

We, however, decided to do the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test, a non-parametric test, as a robust check. The null and alternative hypotheses for this test are

H_0 : the median difference is zero
 H_A : the median difference is not zero

The test statistic is $Z = \frac{W - E(W)}{s.d._w}$

Here $W = \min(W+, W-)$ and $W+$, $W-$ are the sum of positive signed and the sum of negative signed ranks.

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Tables 5,6, and 7 show the calculated test statistics and the associated p-values of the Jarque-Bera test, the ‘paired t-test’, and the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test for the various pairs of indices.

From the table, it is clear that the difference in excess returns on the Sensex and Nifty 50 did not have a normal distribution for any period of the study. The p-values of the ‘paired t test’ and Wilcoxon test indicate that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean and median value of excess returns of the two indices for all periods except for the pre-COVID period.

The null hypothesis of equality in mean and median between BSE 500 and Nifty 500 was not rejected at the conventional level of significance for any period under consideration. The p-values associated with both the parametric and non-parametric tests were very high.

For the pair of indices, the BSE Financial Services and the Nifty Financial Services, the Jarque-Bera test indicates that the distribution of the difference in the excess returns of the two series did not have a normal distribution for all the test periods. At the 5% level of significance, both the parametric and non-parametric tests failed to reject the null hypotheses of no difference in mean and median of the two series for all periods except for the period March 2019 -February 2020.

TABLE 5. TESTS OF NORMALITY AND DIFFERENCE IN MEAN/MEDIAN BETWEEN SENSEX and NIFTY 50

Test Statistic	Aug 2006- April 2010	Aug 2006- July 2007	Aug 2007- April 2009	May 2009- April 2010	Mar 2019- Mar 2023	Mar 2019- Feb 2020	Mar 2020- Mar 2022	April 2022- Mar 2023
Jarque-Bera test	321.6230 (1.45E-70)	6.4644 (3.95E-02)	21.1785 (2.52E-05)	629.0600 (5.19E-138)	4149.26 (0)	0.7366 (6.92E-01)	2740.1300 (0)	190.6620 (3.96E-42)
Paired t-test	-0.2970 (0.7665)	0.1560 (0.8760)	-0.5581 (0.5768)	0.4327 (0.6652)	0.6560 (0.5118)	2.1162 (0.0343)	-0.7080 (0.4790)	0.8779 (0.3800)
Wilcoxon Rank test	-0.6572 (0.5110)	0.0668 (0.9467)	-0.8424 (0.3996)	-0.4417 (0.6587)	0.7126 (0.4761)	2.0443 (0.0409)	-0.7156 (0.4742)	0.5775 (0.5636)

Note: p-values are shown in parentheses

TABLE 6. TESTS OF NORMALITY AND DIFFERENCE IN MEAN/MEDIAN BETWEEN BSE 500 AND NIFTY 500

Test Statistic	Aug 2006 - April 2010	Aug 2006- July 2007	Aug 2007- April 2009	May 2009- April 2010	Mar 2019- Mar 2023	Mar 2019- Feb 2020	Mar 2020- Mar 2022	April 2022- Mar 2023
Jarque-Bera test	124.2260 (1.06E-27)	3.0895 (2.13E-01)	6.7783 (3.37E-02)	79.3774 (5.80E-18)	406487 (0)	27.1167 (1.29E-06)	146325 (0)	0.2819 (8.69E-01)
Paired t-test	0.4491 (0.6533)	1.0703 (0.2845)	-0.6950 (0.4873)	1.2013 (0.2296)	0.3406 (0.7334)	-0.2190 (0.8267)	0.4803 (0.6310)	0.0086 (0.9931)
Wilcoxon Rank test	0.6498 (0.5158)	1.3835 (0.1665)	-0.8412 (0.4002)	1.3901 (0.1645)	0.8671 (0.3859)	-0.0180 (0.9856)	1.1560 (0.2477)	0.0545 (0.9565)

Note: p-values are shown in parentheses

TABLE 7. TESTS OF NORMALITY AND DIFFERENCE IN MEAN/MEDIAN BETWEEN BSE FINANCIAL SERVICES AND NIFTY FINANCIAL SERVICES

Test Statistic	Aug 2006 - April 2010	Aug 2006- July 2007	Aug 2007- April 2009	May 2009- April 2010	Mar 2019- Mar 2023	Mar 2019- Feb 2020	Mar 2020- Mar 2022	April 2022- Mar 2023
Jarque-Bera test	24109.30 (0)	6.7194 (3.47E-02)	31198.10 (0)	637.4530 (3.79E-139)	736.2650 (1.32E-160)	188.0510 (1.46E-41)	435.8200 (2.31E-95)	50.5745 (1.04E-11)
Paired t-test	-0.1861 (0.8524)	-1.1358 (0.2560)	-0.2112 (0.8327)	0.0444 (0.9646)	-1.5776 (0.1147)	-2.4037 (0.0162)	-0.5214 (0.6021)	0.1704 (0.8647)
Wilcoxon Rank test	-0.4449 (0.6564)	-1.1146 (0.2650)	-0.9275 (0.3537)	0.8972 (0.3696)	-0.7229 (0.4697)	-2.2037 (0.0275)	0.1341 (0.8933)	0.6522 (0.5143)

Note: p-values are shown in parentheses

4.4 CORRELATION ANALYSIS

We estimated the correlation coefficient between the various indices to explore the extent to which the excess return series are related. The level of correlation in excess returns between different pairs of indices across all the study periods is shown in Table 8. The correlation between the two benchmark indices and the two broad-based indices across all six possible combinations was higher than 0.95 for all the periods considered. The high degrees of correlation indicate a comovement between similar indices. The comovement between the two benchmark indices, i.e., Sensex and Nifty 50, establishes their role as consistent market indicators.

Indices, in general, had low correlation with both the financial sector indices. For all five indices, the correlation with BSE Financial Services declined dramatically in the post-global financial crisis period. A possible explanation for the decline in correlation, a priori, could be that the financial sector stocks underlying BSE Financial Services showed a slower recovery in contrast to other sectors after the financial chaos. It is, however, difficult to explain this aberrant behaviour without further investigation.

TABLE 8. PAIRWISE CORRELATION BETWEEN INDICES ACROSS ALL THE STUDY PERIODS

Correlation	Aug 2006 - April 2010	Aug 2006- July 2007	Aug 2007- April 2009	May 2009- April 2010	Mar 2019- Mar 2023	Mar 2019- Feb 2020	Mar 2020- Mar 2022	April 2022- Mar 2023
Sensex & BSE 500	0.9809	0.9785	0.9814	0.9806	0.9796	0.9834	0.9832	0.9579
Sensex & BSE Fin Services	0.7410	0.8939	0.8711	0.1899	0.9377	0.9335	0.9418	0.9213
Sensex & NIFTY 50	0.9894	0.9887	0.9884	0.9940	0.9968	0.9958	0.9974	0.9948
Sensex & NIFTY 500	0.9735	0.9732	0.9754	0.9667	0.9792	0.9824	0.9827	0.9580
Sensex & Nifty Fin Services	0.9336	0.8792	0.9428	0.9292	0.9328	0.9232	0.9380	0.9145
BSE 500 & BSE Fin Services	0.7555	0.8957	0.8745	0.2480	0.9215	0.9339	0.9250	0.8976

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BSE 500 & NIFTY 50	0.9836	0.9790	0.9834	0.9871	0.9880	0.9910	0.9898	0.9757
BSE 500 & NIFTY 500	0.9957	0.9954	0.9964	0.9936	0.9997	0.9996	0.9996	0.9998
BSE 500 & Nifty Fin Services	0.9288	0.8770	0.9359	0.9303	0.9044	0.9102	0.9119	0.8623
BSE Fin Services & NIFTY 50	0.7198	0.8690	0.8451	0.1978	0.9325	0.9311	0.9362	0.9170
BSE Fin Services & NIFTY 500	0.7427	0.8783	0.8590	0.2452	0.9219	0.9337	0.9257	0.8975
BSE Fin Services & Nifty Fin Services	0.8074	0.9862	0.9266	0.2723	0.9949	0.9888	0.9966	0.9905
NIFTY 50 & NIFTY 500	0.9857	0.9834	0.9876	0.9807	0.9883	0.9912	0.9901	0.9760
NIFTY 50 & Nifty Fin Services	0.9121	0.8538	0.9181	0.9210	0.9260	0.9190	0.9316	0.9040
NIFTY 500 & Nifty Fin Services	0.9134	0.8599	0.9225	0.9078	0.9055	0.9109	0.9134	0.8623

4.5 GRANGER CAUSALITY TEST

We conducted the Granger Causality Test to examine whether there was any predictive causality between the two benchmark indices. Since the returns on the Nifty Total Market Index are considered as a proxy for returns on the market, we ran a trivariate vector autoregression(VAR) model. The Granger Causality test involved running the following vector autoregression(VAR) model.

$$Sensex_t = \alpha_1 + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_{11,i} Sensex_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_{12,i} Nifty_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_{13,i} Nifty\ TMI_{t-i} + \epsilon_{1t} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$Nifty\ 50_t = \alpha_2 + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_{21,i} Sensex_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_{22,i} Nifty\ 50_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_{23,i} Nifty\ TMI_{t-i} + \epsilon_{2t} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

$$Nifty\ TMI_t = \alpha_3 + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_{31,i} Sensex_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_{32,i} Nifty\ 50_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^l \beta_{33,i} Nifty\ TMI_{t-i} + \epsilon_{3t} \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Since we are interested in examining the dynamic relationship between the two benchmark indices, we examined Granger causality between these two indices only. The Nifty TMI was included to capture broader market

movements, and as the correlation values between Nifty TMI and Sensex, as well as Nifty TMI and Nifty 50, were greater than 0.95 in any period, we felt the market dynamics could be adequately captured by focusing on the benchmark indices themselves. The inclusion of Nifty TMI helped isolate the lead-lag relationship between the Sensex and the Nifty 50 and reduce the possibility of spurious causality arising due to common marketwide shocks.

The null hypotheses are

$$H_0 \text{ for equation (2) is: } \beta_{12,1} = \beta_{12,2} = \beta_{12,3} = \beta_{12,i} = 0$$

$$H_0 \text{ for equation (3) is: } \beta_{22,1} = \beta_{22,2} = \beta_{22,3} = \beta_{22,i} = 0$$

The alternative hypothesis for both equations is that at least one lagged coefficient is non-zero.

The Granger causality test requires that the variables under consideration be stationary and the residuals uncorrelated. Here, 1 is the optimal lag length determined using the minimum AIC criteria. Gretl reports Rao’s F test for autocorrelation in residuals. Table 9 shows the results of Rao’s F-test and the F-test for restrictions on the coefficients of the VAR model.

TABLE 9. GRANGER CAUSALITY TEST BETWEEN SENSEX AND NIFTY 50

F Statistic	Aug 2006 - April 2010	Aug 2006- July 2007	Aug 2007- April 2009	May 2009- April 2010	Mar 2019- Mar 2023	Mar 2019- Feb 2020	Mar 2020- Mar 2022	April 2022- Mar 2023
Rao's F	1.1750 (0.2437)	1.0100 (0.4305)	1.2430 (0.1554)	2.0460 (0.0000)	1.0500 (0.3513)	1.5840 (0.0585)	1.9480 (0.0000)	0.6960 (0.7128)
Nifty 50-> Sensex	1.7702 (0.1512)	0.3590 (0.5496)	0.7403 (0.5649)	2.0897 (0.0087)	1.9148 (0.0341)	1.3400 (0.2638)	1.2708 (0.2628)	2.4980 (0.1153)
Sensex -> Nifty 50	0.2658 (0.8501)	0.1950 (0.6592)	0.3126 (0.8696)	1.6820 (0.0487)	1.8898 (0.0370)	1.6810 (0.1884)	1.0032 (0.4280)	1.3184 (0.2520)

Note: p-values are shown in parentheses

TABLE 10. GRANGER CAUSALITY TEST BETWEEN BSE 500 AND NIFTY 500

F Statistic	Aug 2006 - April 2010	Aug 2006- July 2007	Aug 2007- April 2009	May 2009- April 2010	Mar 2019- Mar 2023	Mar 2019 -Feb 2020	Mar 2020- Mar 2022	April 2022- Mar 2023
Rao's F (p-value)	0.8570 (0.6765)	1.0970 (0.3629)	1.1710 (0.2269)	2.1380 (0.0000)	1.2420 (0.0554)	1.3240 (0.1652)	1.6050 (0.0022)	1.2830 (0.2428)
NIFTY 500 -> BSE 500 (p-value)	1.3581 (0.2543)	1.8395 (0.1763)	0.9010 (0.4633)	0.7047 (0.7960)	1.3083 (0.2142)	2.0369 (0.1327)	2.3884 (0.0207)	0.0270 (0.8697)
BSE 500 -> NIFTY 500 (p-value)	1.8503 (0.1364)	1.3979 (0.2382)	0.5111 (0.7276)	1.4179 (0.1312)	1.4646 (0.1392)	1.7186 (0.1815)	2.1852 (0.0342)	0.0919 (0.7621)

Note: p-values are shown in parentheses

TABLE 11. GRANGER CAUSALITY TEST BETWEEN BSE FINANCIAL SERVICES AND NIFTY FINANCIAL SERVICES

F Statistic	Aug 2006 - April 2010	Aug 2006- July 2007	Aug 2007- April 2009	May 2009- April 2010	Mar 2019- Mar 2023	Mar 2019 -Feb 2020	Mar 2020- Mar 2022	April 2022- Mar 2023
Rao's F (p-value)	2.4640 (0.0000)	1.5850 (0.1162)	1.8660 (0.0016)	2.1580 (0.0000)	1.0820 (0.2747)	0.6820 (0.8311)	1.6270 (0.0017)	1.4800 (0.1518)
Nifty Fin Serv -> BSE Fin Serv	2.7048 (0.0443)	0.0286 (0.8658)	13.4770 (0.0000)	1.2769 (0.2106)	0.5812 (0.8452)	0.7362 (0.4801)	0.4966 (0.8372)	2.7161 (0.1006)
BSE Fin Serv -> Nifty Fin Serv	7.7900 (0.0000)	0.2149 (0.6434)	1.1924 (0.3135)	14.5460 (0.0000)	0.5262 (0.8865)	0.5425 (0.5820)	0.4207 (0.8895)	0.6743 (0.4123)

Note: p-values are shown in parentheses

From Tables 9, 10 and, 11 it is clear that for all three VAR models, the two distinct periods under study, namely May 2009-April 2010 (recovery period after the 2008 crisis) and March 2020-March 2022 (peak COVID period) showed autocorrelation in residuals even when lag lengths were increased beyond what was guided by minimum AIC criteria. The persistence of autocorrelation for lags up to 17 indicates that the structural changes during this period must be taken

into account for drawing inferences regarding Granger causality. For the Granger causality test between the two financial service indices, we note from Table 11 that the null hypothesis of no autocorrelation in the residuals of the VAR model could not be rejected for any of the 2008 crisis periods studied, except for the pre-crisis period of Aug 2006 to July 2007.

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Our study shows that there is no predictive causality between any of the three pairs of indices for the various 2008 crisis periods. This implies that common shocks influenced all indices during the 2008 crisis. For the period overlapping the COVID-19 crisis, there is bidirectional Granger causality between Sensex and Nifty 50. The immediate and widespread policy responses during COVID-19 helped soothe investors’ nerves and created predictability in market movements. However, this predictability was not found for the other two pairs of indices. Interestingly, both the pre-crisis and post-crisis periods of COVID-19 did not show Granger Causality in either direction between Sensex and Nifty 50. Though the sample size in each subperiod is large enough, but if there is only weak causality, the model may not detect it, especially

if the coefficients are unstable. The risk of type-II error, therefore, needs to be further investigated.

4.6 BETA VALUES OF INDICES

To isolate the movements in indices’ returns caused by market-level factors, we calculated the ‘beta’ of each index using equation(1). The Nifty Total Market Index is based on 750 stocks listed on the NSE. These stocks include large cap, mid cap, small cap, and micro cap stocks across sectors, and the Index, therefore, captures broader market movements. The beta values and the associated p-values for various indices in the two periods under study are given below in the Table.

TABLE 12. BETA VALUES OF INDICES

Index	Aug 2006 - April 2010	Aug 2006- July 2007	Aug 2007- April 2009	May 2009- April 2010	Mar 2019- Mar 2023	Mar2019 —Feb 2020	Mar 2020- Mar 2022	April 2022- Mar 2023
Sensex	1.0198 (5.93E-240)	1.0045 (3.47E-115)	1.0234 (1.72E-129)	1.0172 (2.62E-98)	1.0286 (0.00E+00)	0.9799 (1.11E-172)	1.0502 (2.46E-251)	0.9593 (2.03E-104)
BSE 500	1.0043 (0.00E+00)	0.9931 (8.73E-242)	1.0059 (0.00E+00)	1.0029 (2.04E-198)	1.0033 (0.00E+00)	1.0002 (0.00E+00)	1.0050 (0.00E+00)	0.9964 (0.00E+00)
BSE Fin Services	0.9442 (1.09E-37)	1.1238 (1.24E-87)	1.0924 (3.65E-56)	0.3141 (5.00E-04)	1.2420 (5.07E-264)	1.2532 (4.92E-80)	1.2749 (5.23E-149)	1.0603 (6.97E-69)
NIFTY 50	1.0252 (0.00E+00)	1.0402 (7.79E-135)	1.0203 (4.85E-86)	1.0404 (1.15E-119)	1.0236 (0.00E+00)	0.9988 (1.11E-215)	1.0372 (5.26E-306)	0.9739 (8.03E-123)
NIFTY 500	1.0038 (0.00E+00)	1.0030 (0.00E+00)	1.0043 (0.00E+00)	1.0027 (0.00E+00)	1.0001 (0.00E+00)	1.0000 (0.00E+00)	1.0005 (0.00E+00)	0.9978 (0.00E+00)
Nifty Fin Services	1.2024 (2.91E-152)	1.2218 (9.68E-75)	1.2057 (4.85E-86)	1.1807 (2.48E-71)	1.2273 (7.16E-218)	1.2103 (3.77E-64)	1.2685 (1.79E-126)	1.0269 (4.96E-56)

Note: p-values are shown in parentheses

The betas of all the indices were significant for all the periods considered. Since beta measures the volatility in the underlying stocks of an index relative to the broader market index, it is expected that broad-based indices will, in general, have lower beta as compared to indices based on a less diversified group of stocks. While the results of our study do support this behaviour, we also noticed some exceptions. The beta of BSE Financial Services from May 2009 to April 2010 was very low. This low covariance with Nifty TMI is not

surprising, since, as noted earlier, this Index had very low correlation with all the other five indices during this period. Again, for the pre-crisis and post-crisis COVID-19 periods, the beta of Sensex was less than that of BSE 500. Considering that beta varies over time and there might be a structural break during these periods of major economic disturbances, we need a deeper analysis to explain the differences in betas.

4.7 PERFORMANCE OF INDICES ACROSS PHASES OF MARKET DISTURBANCES

To compare the performance of indices, we calculated three risk-adjusted return measures- the Sharpe Ratio, Treynor Ratio, and Sortino Ratio. The three ratios differ in the way risk is defined. The Sharpe Ratio uses s.d. in returns as a measure of risk and reflects the total volatility in the excess returns of indices. The Sortino Ratio, on the other hand, treats

only losses from investment and not total variations in returns as risk. The s.d. in negative returns is therefore the measure of risk here. The Treynor Ratio uses beta as a measure of risk, and returns on the asset would, therefore, compensate only for systematic risk and not total risk.

The three ratios for the various periods studied are given in Tables 13, 14, and 15.

TABLE 13. RISK-ADJUSTED RETURNS ON INDICES FOR THE TWO CRISIS PERIODS

	Aug 2006 - April 2010			Mar 2019- Mar 2023		
Index	SHARPE Ratio	SORTINO Ratio	TREYNOR Ratio	SHARPE Ratio	SORTINO Ratio	TREYNOR Ratio
Sensex	2.106E-02	2.8591E-02	4.2783E-04	3.118E-02	3.566E-02	4.0317E-04
BSE 500	2.556E-02	3.2385E-02	5.0692E-04	3.207E-02	3.533E-02	4.0528E-04
BSE Fin Services	3.137E-02	4.3051E-02	8.3393E-04	1.802E-02	2.072E-02	2.4718E-04
NIFTY 50	2.265E-02	2.9968E-02	4.5425E-04	2.998E-02	3.418E-02	3.8366E-04
NIFTY 500	2.431E-02	3.0792E-02	4.8008E-04	3.192E-02	3.511E-02	4.0308E-04
Nifty Fin Services~	3.399E-02	4.7590E-02	7.3578E-04	2.288E-02	2.668E-02	3.1998E-04

TABLE 14. RISK-ADJUSTED RETURNS ON INDICES FOR THE GLOBAL FINANCIAL CRISIS PERIOD

	Aug 2006- July 2007			Aug 2007- April 2009			May 2009- April 2010		
Index	SHARPE Ratio	SORTINO Ratio	TREYNOR Ratio	SHARPE Ratio	SORTINO Ratio	TREYNOR Ratio	SHARPE Ratio	SORTINO Ratio	TREYNOR Ratio
Sensex	1.158E-01	1.379E-01	1.383E-03	-3.204E-02	-4.628E-02	-8.036E-04	9.281E-02	1.691E-01	1.624E-03
BSE 500	1.334E-01	1.504E-01	1.556E-03	-4.011E-02	-5.403E-02	-9.834E-04	1.205E-01	1.978E-01	2.049E-03
BSE Fin Services	1.411E-01	1.796E-01	1.867E-03	-3.206E-02	-4.784E-02	-9.123E-04	1.197E-01	2.051E-01	8.122E-03
NIFTY 50	1.116E-01	1.312E-01	1.318E-03	-2.837E-02	-3.935E-02	-7.026E-04	8.902E-02	1.564E-01	1.535E-03
NIFTY 500	1.261E-01	1.436E-01	1.465E-03	-3.743E-02	-5.047E-02	-9.147E-04	1.127E-01	1.826E-01	1.903E-03
Nifty Fin Services	1.404E-01	1.835E-01	1.898E-03	-2.730E-02	-4.186E-02	-7.239E-04	1.126E-01	1.900E-01	2.098E-03

TABLE 15. RISK-ADJUSTED RETURNS ON INDICES FOR THE COVID-19 PERIOD

	Mar2019-Feb 2020			Mar 2020- Mar 2022			April 2022- Mar 2023		
Index	SHARPE Ratio	SORTINO Ratio	TREYNOR Ratio	SHARPE Ratio	SORTINO Ratio	TREYNOR Ratio	SHARPE Ratio	SORTINO Ratio	TREYNOR Ratio
Sensex	1.966E-02	3.172E-02	1.858E-04	4.597E-02	4.830E-02	7.100E-04	-4.830E-03	-7.678E-03	-4.698E-05

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BSE 500	3.940E-03	6.186E-03	3.655E-05	5.622E-02	5.560E-02	8.525E-04	-1.791E-02	-2.614E-02	-1.663E-04
BSE Fin Services	3.222E-02	4.881E-02	3.201E-04	1.616E-02	1.790E-02	2.649E-04	1.368E-02	1.996E-02	1.419E-04
NIFTY 50	7.104E-03	1.142E-02	6.653E-05	4.925E-02	5.108E-02	7.549E-04	-1.057E-02	-1.659E-02	-1.008E-04
NIFTY 500	4.339E-03	6.820E-03	4.024E-05	5.594E-02	5.536E-02	8.477E-04	-1.790E-02	-2.611E-02	-1.662E-04
Nifty Fin Services	5.572E-02	8.358E-02	5.676E-04	1.792E-02	2.024E-02	2.978E-04	1.206E-02	1.808E-02	1.305E-04

Table 12 indicates that the performance of all six indices dropped during the August 2007 to April 2009 period in terms of all three ratios. This is to be expected given that all the indices were underperforming compared to a return on our proxy for riskless return, i.e., the savings account. A comparison of performances during the pre-crisis and the recovery period of the 2008 crisis shows that all indices performed better in terms of the Sortino and the Treynor ratio but worse in terms of the Sharpe ratio. This indicates that the downside risk to investments in Index Funds and Exchange-Traded Funds that mimicked these indices had come down. As is evident from Table 13 for the COVID-19 period, benchmark indices and broad-based indices delivered a better risk-adjusted return during the peak pandemic period as compared to the pre-pandemic period. The increase in interest rates in the post-pandemic period made investing in stock markets highly unattractive.

4.6 CONCLUSIONS

Stock market Indices reflect the market participants’ outlook on the country’s economic prospects and are important indicators influencing investment in stocks. The performance of indices in terms of mean excess returns during the two crises highlights the stabilizing role of fiscal and monetary policy measures. When policy responses were swift and widespread, as during the COVID-19 crisis, it helped improve market sentiments, and returns on indices increased even during the peak crisis period. Credible and unambiguous policy interventions during the pandemic reduced uncertainty, as reflected in statistically significant bidirectional predictive causality between Sensex and Nifty 50. Lessons drawn from the returns behaviour will be of great help in handling the increased uncertainties during any such future crisis.

The correlation of benchmark indices and broad-based indices was lower with the financial services index than among themselves. Investors can therefore have a better risk-return outcome on their portfolios by combining financial sector equities with stocks underlying broad-based indices. However, correlation analysis and statistical tests comparing the mean and median excess returns of similarly composed

indices revealed no significant diversification benefits from investing across the two exchanges.

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